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PROGRAM BRAZIL VOLUNTEER. CULTURE OF VOLUNTEERING THROUGH DISTANCE EDUCATION

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The Brazil Volunteer, volunteer program of the Brazilian government, was created to meet the FIFA Confederations Cup held in Brazil in 2013 and the FIFA World Cup to be held in Brazil in 2014. The event will be held in 12 Brazilian host cities and will have the assistance of volunteer residents of these cities. The role of the volunteers will be integrated with the volunteer program of FIFA and work as an extensive network of mobilization, which will operate in points mobility, airports, public viewing events, flow areas, around the stadiums and open media centers. In these places, they will support the target audience attendance: fans, unaccredited media, tourists and the general population. (Brasil Voluntario 2014). The Brazil Volunteer program featured a distance course planned by the Education Centre Distance the University of Brasília - UNB-CEAD using free software Moodle, content teachers from the university and a multidisciplinary team for a public of course participants present in twelve Brazilian cities, called host cities.

keywords: [ead](#), [distance education](#), [volunteer](#).